

The level of satisfaction of the fans of “The Notebook” movie version in Region 4-A CALABARZON

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Abstract

Movie adaptations of best-selling books are a big part of the film industry, but most of the time, fans are not satisfied with its adaptation. However, The Notebook film adaptation is considered the most successful adaptation of the novels written by Nicholas Sparks. The purpose of this study is to assess the satisfaction of fans with the film adaptation of “The Notebook.” The researchers utilized survey questionnaires to rate and evaluate the level of satisfaction of the fans. Using a Pearson Product-moment correlation as the statistical tool of this research, this study analyzed the level of satisfaction of the fans of “The Notebook” to its movie adaptation. The film has a high level of satisfaction among those who have seen it. The survey revealed that the respondents' satisfaction with the film is high; they gave a satisfactory rating to the storyline and a high satisfactory rating to the characters and settings of the film. Moreover, the age and gender of the respondents have no bearing on their satisfaction with the movie. This study definitively answered the fans' satisfaction level of “The Notebook” into its film adaptation. Furthermore, research must be done on different movie adaptations to fully understand fans' level of satisfaction in the novels' movie adaptations.

Keywords: *Film adaptations; Satisfaction; Books; Characters; Settings.*

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Introduction

“*The Notebook*” begins in 1946, amid the austere beauty of coastal North Carolina, with the story of Noah Calhoun, a rural Southerner who returned home after World War II. This article will examine Marxism through the lens of Karl Marx's theory of their experiences in the film. In “*The Notebook*,” Nicholas Sparks' novel of the same name. The main characters are Noah Calhoun and Allison Hamilton (Allie), a young couple who fall in love in 1940. Their story is narrated by an older man (old Noah) to a fellow nursing home resident from the current day.

Allie is the daughter of an affluent family, and she is kind and attractive. She initially met Noah while hanging out with her buddies at the amusement park. Noah was the first to express his interest in Allie, and he approached her and said he wanted to go on a date with her. Allie is unconcerned about him because she knows Noah is a stranger who wants to flirt with her. After a long time, Noah and Allie became a couple. This is not the end of their relationship; they must fight for permission from Allie's parents.

Allie and Noah are from opposite socio-economic classes; Allie comes from an affluent family, while Noah is a destitute man who lives with his elderly father. Allie's parents are aware of her connection. They do not permit them because Noah is merely a laborer who does not fit in with their family.

The class conflict has a significant impact on the relationship's longevity. The movie recounted the story of the lovers, Allie and Noah, who were trying to justify their love despite their social class differences. This film features Marxist concerns that illustrate the battles in the characters' love due to their disparities in class standing and have created all sorts of troubles for them.

Nicholas Sparks' novel "*The Notebook*" is well-known. The book is about the love story of two couples who have gone through horrible events in their lives. Alzheimer's disease was diagnosed to the lady, which prompts the gentleman to read a notebook containing the narrative of how they met to preserve and restore their memories of them together. The novel was first published on October 1, 1996.

According to Ruetten (2017), "*The Notebook*" is not a typical love narrative that does not become unforgettable to audiences, but rather the film becomes memorable in every detail. The film's plot has been ranked as one of the best love stories ever written. Ruetten even raised the most important question: "*Is love still there if all the memories are gone?*" The film has inspired and motivated people to take risks, even when it appears to be impossible.

The cinematic adaptation of Nicholas Sparks' novel "*The Notebook*" is widely regarded as his most successful work. The picture grossed over \$116 million globally, according to Devoe et al. (2021). It even received MTV's Best Kiss Award. They even mentioned how unusual "*The Notebook*" is. A true story inspires it. The grandparents of Nicholas Sparks' ex-wife were the inspiration for the story. It shows the story of how his ex-wife's grandparents met and married.

The researcher has chosen to evaluate the level of satisfaction of the majority of film adaptation viewers. The researchers have decided to conduct a study to measure the level of satisfaction among "*The Notebook*" fans in Region IV-A (Calabarzon). They employed guide questions to assess fans' satisfaction with the film adaptation of "The Notebook," which will serve as a step-by-step collection of necessary data. Beauty Theory's aid and support will help indicate how film spectators might be joyful due to the film's attractiveness. As a result, they examined and assessed whether the novel's film adaptation is true and substantial.

Literature taught researchers that cinema adaptations rarely satisfy novel fans. Movies with skillfully adapted screenplays from books, short tales, and plays can be a valuable element of lesson planning. The researchers can incorporate film adaptations into the learning process using the strategies indicated above.

The study of a film adaptation of a literary work will demonstrate how words are converted to visual media, allowing us to compare the written original to the cinematic version and highlighting the strategies of both film and the written word in presenting a tale. Presenting a high-production-value cinematic adaptation will demonstrate that movies may be an art form that communicates differently than the written word but is no less essential.

Furthermore, when used as a reward for reading a novel, a filmed adaptation can highlight that novel-length works of fiction typically contain a plethora of detail, information, and plotlines that are missed in a film. For all of these reasons, film adaptations of novels, short stories, or plays are ideal resources for classroom assignments that require students to learn and practice analytical and writing abilities.

According to studies and movie reviews, most movie adaptations fail to outperform their premise; nonetheless, *The Notebook* was rated successful based on the reviews and movie gross (Jenjindawong, 2017). Based on the preliminary investigation of related literature, researchers discovered that no research on the subject had yet been undertaken.

To determine the level of satisfaction of notebook fans with the film adaptation, researchers used guide questions that can serve as a step-by-step collection of required data. Researchers analyzed the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age and gender. They will assess the respondents' level

of satisfaction in terms of the storyline, characters, and locations. Furthermore, the researchers looked at the relationship between respondents' levels of satisfaction and their demographic profile.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to assess the satisfaction of fans with the film adaptation of “The Notebook.” In Region 4-A Calabarzon specifically, it seeks answers to the following:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - Age
 - Gender
2. What is the level of satisfaction of the respondents to the movie in terms of:
 - Storyline
 - Characters
 - Settings
3. What is the association between the level of satisfaction and the demographic profile of the respondents?

Methodology

This study is designed as a quantitative study, described as a process of collecting and evaluating numerical data. It can identify trends and averages, make predictions, verify causal links, and extrapolate results to larger groups (Bhandari, 2020). The study utilizes a descriptive research method. Descriptive research is a quantitative study that aims to collect measurable data to do statistical analysis on a population sample. It is a widely used market research instrument that allows us to collect and define the characteristics of a demographic category (McCombes, 2019). In the current study, the researcher aims to describe the satisfaction of the fans of the novel “*The Notebook*” with the film adaptation. To describe the fans' perception, the researcher has utilized a quantitative method of data gathering that uses survey questionnaires to gather data and represent a phenomenon.

The researcher's sample in the present study comprises the fans of the novel “*The Notebook*” settled in Region IV-A, Calabarzon. The sample is picked through the convenience sampling technique. In this technique, a sample is taken in accordance with the target participant's convenience and availability (Roller & Lavrakas, 2018). Convenience sampling is used by researchers not just because it is simple to use but also because it has additional research benefits. It allows the researcher to acquire primary data and trends about the study without the hassles that come with employing a randomized sample. A total of 82 respondents were utilized in the study to ensure its validity and reliability.

The researchers have formulated some survey questions, which were transferred to Google Forms. The researcher identifies currently available samples and is willing to cooperate on the data gathering process in the Facebook group “*The Notebook Novel by Nicholas Sparks*.” Researchers also picked random people to ensure that the samples are fans of The Notebook novel. The researchers considered their availability and their convenience in participating in the study.

The study utilized a quantitative method of data gathering. In a quantitative method of data gathering, survey questionnaires are used and are self-made. According to Tetali et al. (2015), the self-made questionnaire is a structured questionnaire that includes both closed-ended and open-ended questions. It is called self-administered since respondents fill it out without the assistance of an interviewer. Instead of going long distances to meet with samples or hiring face-to-face interviewers, researchers simply send sample questionnaires and conveniently collect the data online in accordance with the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) health protocols. To assure its authenticity, the researchers sought the help of the statistician in validating the instrument. After validation, they sought approval from the adviser to use the instrument. The tools were ensured to be authentic, valid, and approved by the thesis adviser and the statistician.

The study was initiated as soon as the approval of the title was permitted by the thesis adviser. Once approved, researchers formulate survey questions through Google Forms. The researchers send a letter of request to the following participants to conduct a study: After the response has been received, the distribution of the survey questionnaire will immediately proceed. After distribution, the researchers ensure that all blanks are filled out and thoroughly answered. After gathering the responses, the researcher tallied the results and forwarded the data to the statistician to make treatments on data analysis and to help formulate the conclusions and recommendations. Once the data is analyzed, the research presents the results and summarizes all the findings. From the results and findings, the researchers came up with a conclusion and built appropriate recommendations based on the findings of the study.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Frequency table of the respondents' age (N=82)

Age	Frequency	Percentage
23-27 years old	60	73.2
28-32 years old	16	19.5
Above 32 years old	6	7.3

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to age. Among the 82 respondents, 60 are 23-27 years old, representing 73.2%, followed by the respondents who are 28-32 years old, representing 19.5%, and above 32 years old, representing 7.3%.

This table shows that most participants are between 23 and 27 years old, with 60 or 70.2% of total respondents. Researchers found out that ages 23–27 have the greatest number of respondents. Younger millennials, ages 23–27, are a growing population of book lovers, according to Haq (2012). The study also showed some surprising facts about how young readers use e-books. For starters, younger readers are more into digital materials, yet they are not abandoning print books for digital.

Table 2. Frequency table of the respondents' gender (N=82)

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	55	67.1
Male	27	32.9

Table 2 shows the total number and percentage of the male and female respondents from Region IV-A CALABARZON. There are 27 male and 55 female respondents, for a total of 82 respondents. Female respondents comprise a more significant percentage (67.1%) compared to males (32.9%).

This table implies that the majority of the respondents are female. Results revealed that there are more females who read the novel than males. According to the study of Wühr and Schwarz (2016), men remembered more details from action movies than women, and women remembered more information from romantic films than men (as cited by Dolan, 2017).

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of the level of satisfaction to the movie: The Notebook (N=82)

Level of Satisfaction	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Storyline	4.25	.51	Satisfied
Characters	4.41	.58	Highly Satisfied
Settings	4.36	.55	Highly Satisfied
Overall	4.34	.49	Highly Satisfied

Legend: 4.21-5.00 – Highly Satisfied; 3.41-4.20 – Satisfied; 2.61-3.40 – Moderately Satisfied; 1.81-2.60 – Slightly Satisfied; 1.00-1.80 – Not Satisfied

The results of the descriptive statistics of the respondents' level of satisfaction with the movie, The Notebook, showed satisfied to highly satisfied levels. This reveals that those who watched the film find the vibe and the storyline satisfactory and attractive (M = 4.25, SD = .51) with a verbal interpretation of 'satisfied.' This result also suggests that the respondents found the characters (M = 4.41, SD = .58) with a verbal interpretation of 'highly satisfied' and the settings (M = 4.36, SD = .55) of the movie very pleasing and highly satisfactory.

Moreover, the overall weighted mean of satisfaction in the movie (The Notebook) is 4.34, which indicates that the study participants were highly attracted to the film. The storyline received a satisfactory rating from respondents. The movie adaptation failed to receive a high satisfactory rating in the storyline since movie makers have to cut subplots to make the film remain watchable (Morgan, 2018). On the other hand, respondents gave a high satisfactory rating for characters and settings; even though subplots have been changed, the characters and settings of the "*The Notebook*" movie adaptation remain the same compared to the novel (Ebert, 2004).

Table 4. Correlation analysis between the respondents' level of satisfaction and demographic profiles

	Age	Gender	Storyline	Characters	Settings	Overall
Age	-					
Gender	-0.095	-				
Storyline	-0.025	0.011	-			
Characters	0.031	-0.121	.740**	-		
Settings	-0.006	-0.02	.721**	.718**	-	
Overall	0.001	-0.051	.900**	.912**	.900**	-

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The researchers computed Pearson correlation using SPSS version 26 to analyze if there is a correlation between the demographic profiles (i.e., age and gender) and the level of satisfaction of the respondents to the movie The Notebook. The results reveal that there was no relationship or association between age and the elements of the movie: storyline ($r = -.025$, $p = .822$); characters ($r = .031$, $p = .783$); settings ($r = -.006$, $p = .955$); and overall scores ($r = .001$, $p = .995$). Likewise, the results indicate that there is no association between gender and all the elements of the movie: storyline ($r = .011$, $p = .920$); characters ($r = -.121$, $p = .279$); settings ($r = -.020$, $p = .861$); and overall scores ($r = -.051$, $p = .649$).

These results suggest that the level of satisfaction and the attractiveness of the movie "*The Notebook*" may not be explained by either age or gender. This means that people are pleased and highly satisfied with all the movie elements, regardless of their age or gender.

Researchers discovered that younger millennials, ages 23–27, are an increasing community of book lovers, according to Haq (2012). The research also revealed some interesting facts regarding how young readers interact with e-books. For starters, younger readers prefer digital materials over print books, but they are not entirely abandoning them.

Additionally, results revealed that more females than males had read the novel. Men remembered more details from action movies than women, according to Wühr & Schwarz (2016), and women

remembered more details from romance movies than men. Moreover, respondents gave a satisfactory rating to the storyline. Still, the movie adaptation did not obtain a highly satisfied rating in the storyline because the moviemakers needed to eliminate subplots to keep the movie enjoyable (Morgan, 2018). Respondents, on the other hand, gave the notebook movie version a high satisfactory rating in terms of characters and settings; even though subplots were changed, characters and settings remained the same as in the novel, according to Ebert (2004), which proves that ‘*The Notebook*’ movie adaptation has met the expectations of the fans that make the film attractive to the viewers and make them satisfied with the film.

Conclusion

In terms of the profile of the respondents, most of the fans of *The Notebook* were aged between 23 and 27 years old. In terms of their gender, most of them were female. 60 of the 82 respondents are between the ages of 23 and 27, representing 73.2%, followed by respondents between the ages of 28 and 32, representing 19.5 percent, and those over 32, representing 7.3 percent. There are 82 responses in total, with 27 males and 55 females. In comparison to male respondents, female respondents account for a higher percentage (67.1%).

The survey revealed that the respondents' satisfaction with the film's settings and characters is high; on the other hand, they gave a satisfactory rating in terms of the storyline. “*The Notebook*” showed satisfied to highly satisfied levels. This reveals that those who watched the movie find the vibe and the storyline satisfactory and attractive ($M = 4.25$, $SD = .51$) with a verbal interpretation of ‘satisfied.’ This result also suggests that the respondents found the characters ($M = 4.41$, $SD = .58$) with a verbal interpretation of ‘highly satisfied’ and the settings ($M = 4.36$, $SD = .55$) of the movie very pleasing and highly satisfactory.

Results revealed that neither age nor gender can predict the level of satisfaction and attractiveness of the film *The Notebook*. This indicates that everyone, regardless of age or gender, is pleased and satisfied with all aspects of the film. The results reveal that there was no relationship or association between age and the elements of the movie: storyline ($r = -.025$, $p = .822$); characters ($r = .031$, $p = .783$); settings ($r = -.006$, $p = .955$); and overall scores ($r = .001$, $p = .995$). Likewise, the results indicate that there is no association between gender and all the elements of the movie: storyline ($r = .011$, $p = .920$); characters ($r = -.121$, $p = .279$); settings ($r = -.020$, $p = .861$); and overall scores ($r = -.051$, $p = .649$).

Based on the results of the study, the researchers conclude that the satisfaction of the respondents with the films is not influenced by age or gender. The level of satisfaction of the respondents was mainly affected by the setting, characters, and storyline of the film. This only shows that a film enthusiast is usually captivated and satisfied by the settings, characters, and storyline based entirely on the novel.

Additionally, respondents showed a greater satisfaction level with the storyline than the setting and characters, proving that the movie maker's subplot-cutting strategy impacts the fans' satisfaction level. The characters and settings in the *Notebook* movie adaptation are identical to those in the novel, hence why fans rated those two aspects highly satisfied.

Moreover, researchers found out that respondents are highly satisfied with the movie adaptation of “*The Notebook*,” which shows that the public's reaction reveals that the film has earned a great deal of satisfaction. When the film attracts the audience, expectations are met, which leads to a positive response, as is the level of satisfaction. As a result, the attractiveness of a film leads to fan satisfaction.

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